

Ayurvedic and Medical Tourism

Dr. Sr. Kritikaa

Assistant Professor, Jayendra Saraswathi College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Build in India initiative will contribute to the growth of medical tourism phenomenally for several reasons. Health checks visiting the attractions, identical with the words like health tourism, remedial journey or inclusive healthcare and have become a universal concept gaining importance. The word was first used by travel agencies and is today used by media, government, tourism development corporations etc. The countries which have become the best destination include Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia and India for Healthcare also sometimes referred to as Healthcare Hub. The investigation focuses the involvement of two of the 25 zones notorious via seeing the sights & generosity and Wellness which will be the driver for its growth. The data is collected from the secondary sources and extensive literature review brings out the several factors which will be a thrust to the Medical Tourism. The case takes into account the analysis of future developments in areas of demographic, social and economics which will show the outcome of the holder.

How to cite this paper: Sr. Kritikaa "Ayurvedic and Medical Tourism" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-3, April 2020, pp.927-931, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd30756.pdf

IJTSRD30756

Copyright © 2020 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

INTRODUCTION

The Make in India initiative of Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi was launched as a program in September 2014 for comprehensive and expansive nation-building with an objective to make India an attractive destination for manufacturing and transform it into manufacturing-hub. It has claimed to over-haul outdated processes and policies with a claim of „Minimum Government, Maximum Governance. The plan was to increase the confidence of Indian entrepreneurs and citizens and also the global potential partners who can consider India as the preferred destination, provide a framework for a vast amount of technical information on 25 industry sectors: and communicate effectively and regularly to local and global audience through social media about the reforms and opportunities. To execute „Make in India“ initiative, the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) along with specialized agencies has taken comprehensive efforts to create the awareness of the program and information dissemination about the 25 sectors viz. coupé motor apparatus, Aviation, manipulation free exiting Construction, Defence Manufacturing, Electrical Machinery, Electronic System, Food Processing, Information Technology & Business Process Management (IT & BPM), Leather, Media & Entertainment, Mining, oil & gossip Pertaining, cushy & trucked , track line, emission Energy, infrastructure & Highways, Space, Textiles & Garments, Thermal Power, Tourism & Hospitality and Wellness. Detailed brochures were developed for all the identified sectors with key facts and figures, policies and initiatives and sector-specific contact details. DIPP in full swing the progression of appealing participation from several concerned entities like industry leaders, Union Ministers, Secretaries to the

Government of India, State Governments and several knowledge partners to formulate an action plan for the next three years, aimed at raising the manufacturing sector to 25% of the GDP by 2020. This entire process resulted into the historical initiative i.e. Make in India program with a unique feature of public-private partnership (PPP). Within 17 months of this initiative India has seen several moves such as, in Electronics sector, Foxconn, the manufacturer of Apples phone has announced plans for creating 10 to 12 facilities in India. In Automobile sector Mercedes Benz has decided to manufacture its luxury buses in India, to be exported to Africa and South East Asian markets. Volvo and BMW have also decided to increase its localization. In defence sector, Hyundai Heavy Industries (HHI) of South Korea will work with Hindustan Shipyard Ltd, Vizag to build warships in India. Samsung, South Korea, has also agreed to build LNG tankers with Kochi Shipyard. Six industrial corridors are being developed across several parts of the country. Industrial cities determination also comes up along these funnelled.

Medical tourism in India:

Medical visiting the attractions in India is proposed to be a US\$9 billion instance adjacent to 2020. Currently, medical tourism industry is pegged at US\$3 billion. Globally, the medical tourism market is approximate at around US\$40-60 billion. Confer to the association of Indian Industries the as a rule important intention that grab remedial value voyage to India is cost-effectiveness, and treatment from accredited facilities at equivalence with urbanized countries at a great deal inferior fee. India at present defences 5th on the Medical Tourism Index globally and 2nd in Asia as per the

International Healthcare and Research Centre statistics. This illustrate impending occasion for India in flattering a future leader in medical tourism specified the reality that it focuses on building infrastructure, technology & services, and a seamless experience for buyers.

Significance of the Study Area

India has become a hub for medical tourism in South East Asia. It is because many of the states of India have identified the potential of the medical tourism business and taken up this opportunity to materialize on it. In other words medical tourism has grown as the outcome of changes in the institutional context of medical care, a more global economics of access to health and new attitudes to personal identity and medical care, enabled by developments in international communication, transport and tourism. Going overseas for medical treatments gives international patients the opportunity to encounter cost-effective, immediate and high-end health care alternatives¹. Owing to the increased tourist flow and the significance of the medical tourism a need is felt to position Coimbatore as a medical tourism business centre. The same could be possible only if the perception of the foreign tourists and NRI's are taken into consideration since they are the target customers for medical tourism. This would make us aware of the prospects of Coimbatore city emerging as a medical tourism destination².

Scope for the Study:

Medical tourism is an emerging trend in the tourism industry with the privatization of health care services. Especially it is gaining prominence in developing countries like India. It is different from other conventional forms of tourism as it is not destination tourism but medical health package tourism. The Indian healthcare industry is growing at a tremendous pace due to its strengthening coverage, services and increasing expenditure by public as well private players. The study is confined to the Coimbatore city. Moreover, it will highlight on the future trends and treatment practices of medical tourism.

Following objectives are framed for the effective conduct of the study:

- To understand demographic segmentation of medical tourist, who travel to Coimbatore city?
- To analysis the tourist level of awareness towards ayurvedic treatment and its health care benefits.
- To assess the ayurvedic treatment utilising practices among domestic and international tourist patients.
- To identify the primary reason stated by the tourist for selecting a specific ayurvedic center in Coimbatore.
- To measure the tourist level of satisfaction towards ayurvedic treatment and the services offered at the specific center.

¹ Pamela Landreville (2016), Middle Eastern Consumers' Perceptions Towards Medical Tourism In Thailand, The Bangkok Medical Journal Volume. No. 12, PP:39-51

² C Shanthi Marie and Sampad Kumar Swain (2012), A Study on Customer Perception of Medical Tourism in Puducherry, AJTS, 7, 1, ISSN 0975-3281, PP: 59-75

Jagasia (2008)³ in his study on medical tourism in India – A Report, tells that medical tourism provides private medical care in collaboration with tourism industry to patients from other countries. In India, bulk of patients comes from neighboring countries such as Bangladesh, Pakistan, other Asian Countries, Africa, and Middle East Countries but health care industry has some inherent drawbacks. Lack of standardization in medical care and cost, lack of regulatory mechanism, infrastructural bottlenecks, and poor medical insurance coverage are a few to mention here. On the other hand, tourism industry and hospitality industry are facing some major challenges to develop the infrastructure and services. In this situation, Indian Government encourages medical tourism through low-cost but excellent medical treatment for the travellers who come from foreign countries to India. This study also helps to understand the real situation of medical tourism in India.

Marie and Swain (2012)⁴ study aimed to analyse the Customer Perception of Medical Tourism in Pondicherry The findings of the study revealed that majority of the hospitals do marketing overseas through word of mouth and the MOU with government especially the trust hospitals, possibly corporate hospitals are also concentrating on hospital tie-ups, advertisements, newspaper articles, travel agency websites, representative office and agents in other country.

Qadeer and Reddy (2013)⁵ study aimed to explores their perceptions of medical tourism (MT) within India which is a complex process involving international demands and policy shifts from service to commercialisation of health care for trade, gross domestic profit, and foreign exchange. The paper highlights the differences and similarities in the perceptions and context of the two sets of physicians, presents evidence, that questions the support for MT and finally analyzes some

³ Sonam Jagasia (2008), Medical Tourism in India – A Report, Acumen, Volume. No. Issue. No.2, PP.13 – 17.

⁴ Fredrick (2009)³ study aimed to analyse, medical tourism in India, gives information under the headings of the growth of medical tourism, nature of medical tourism and major problems of medical tourism. The study tells that India is one of the best places for all types of health care treatment. Therefore, people around the world have considered India as the 'Global Health Destination'. Based on the recent trends medical tourism will continue to expand in the years ahead and India will emerge as one of the leading nations specializing in the field.

⁵ Arwar et al. (2012)³ examined the relationship between the key elements of medical tourist's perception and its impact on destination selection by developing a conceptual research model and the results revealed that cost, service quality, treatment types and availability, lack of access to particular treatment and marketing impact had a very strong relationship on the perception of medical tourist's in selecting the destination.

⁴ Shanthi Marie and Sampad Kumar Swain (2012), A Study on Customer Perception of Medical Tourism in Pondicherry, Asian Journal of Tranfusion Science, Volume. No. 7, Issue. No. 1, ISSN 0975-3281, PP. 59-75.

⁵ Imrana Qadeer and Sunita Reddy (2013), Medical tourism in India: perceptions of physicians in tertiary care hospitals, Qadeer and Reddy Philosophy, Ethics, and Humanities in Medicine, Volume. No. 8, Issue. No. 20, PP.1-10.

key implications of MT on Indian health services, ethical issues emerging out of that and the need for understanding the linkages between public and private sectors for a more effective intervention for an equitable medical care policy.

Sharma (2013)⁶ study aimed to highlight the potential of Medical Tourism industry in India. Research study we tried to find out the positive economic benefits of medical tourism and to focus the role of government, ministry of tourism, pharmaceuticals industries, and private sector to build the image of India as high quality medical tourism destination. The study concluded that India is in an advantageous position to tap the global opportunities in the medical tourism sector. Bindu and Sivakami (2016)⁷ study aimed to focus the service quality of ayurvedic centres in Palakkad city of Kerala. The study found that the perception of services received by the customers is just about their expectation leaving very little positive gap in the service delivery. Findings of the study revealed that the treatment and services provided at the health care centres of Palakkad, Kerala are satisfactory with a scope of improvement for better services in future. The results of the study unveil the vital role of effective service delivery in customer satisfaction of health tourism practice of ayurvedic centers of Palakkad which needs to be tapped effectively to pave way for sustainable tourism development in the state.

Kaboor and Somashekar (2018)⁸ study aimed to analyse the customer perception towards health tourism in Karnataka. The result showed that, Internet and media have very high perception score as compared to the other sources of awareness of health resorts. There is no difference in the overall mean perception score about health tourism among group of respondents. The study findings also revealed that customer perception and customer satisfaction are the direct antecedent of customer retention. The study concluded that health tourism business usually becomes highly volatile and sensitive due to the fundamental nature of tourism business. The study found that planners and marketing designers should promote the health tourism without losing its serenity.

Need for Medical Tourism:

Remedial tourism has become a familiar form of recreation, or travel, and concealment, broad spectrum of medical services. It mixes leisure, fun and relaxation together with wellness and healthcare. The initiative of the healthiness holiday is to tender you an occasion to dig up away from your daily routine and come into different relaxing surroundings. Here, you can enjoy being close to the

beaches and mountains. At the same time you are able to receive an orientation that will help you improve your life in terms of your health and general well-being. It is like rejuvenation and cleanup process at all the levels- physical, mental and emotional. Numerous public commencing the residential world get nearer to India for the renewal promised by yoga and Ayurvedic massage, but only a few consider it a destination for hip replacement or brain surgery. On the other hand a fussy amalgamate of top-class remedial capability at attractive prices is helping a growing number of Indian corporate hospitals lure foreign patients, including a the minority from residential nations such as UK and the US.

Vision and Mission of the Ministry:-

The Vision of the Ministry is to position AYUSH systems as the preferred systems of living and practice for Attaining a healthy India. The Ministry has identified its Mission in terms of seven broad thematic areas of AYUSH activities. The thematic areas are as follows:

A. Effective Human Resource Development:-

- To ensure availability of quality education and training to AYUSH Doctors/Scientists/Teachers;
- To ensure availability of quality paramedical, pharmacy and nursing education and training
- In AYUSH;
- To provide opportunity for quality AYUSH education throughout the country;
- To empower AYUSH professionals with improved skills and attitudes; and
- To promote capacity building of Institutions, Centres of Excellence (COE), National Institutes etc.

Ayurveda:

Ayurveda is a holistic system of healing that has a tradition of 3000 years old. Kerala and Ayurveda are synonymous to each other, as it is the only place on earth where Ayurveda is practised with absolute authenticity and dedication. This ancient Indian system of medicine has proved to be not only the cure for illness but also the 100 percent natural way to perfect health. The methods of Ayurveda are unique and universal. Instead of treating the symptoms of a disease, it treats the individual and caring is given for the entire body. Ayurveda medicines are purely natural and absolutely free of side effects.

Role of Ayurveda in Health Tourism:

Ayurveda is one of the components of health tourism and it is the main contributor to Kerala's health tourism. Ayurveda and Kerala are synonymous to each other. It is the trade mark of Kerala's health tourism. It is a holistic 144 treatment that has no side effects and hence it is very popular among health care travellers. The treatment under Ayurveda helps to rejuvenate body and mind. One can take holiday and rejuvenate his body and mind undergoing Ayurveda treatment. Not only health tourists but also tourists coming with some other specific purposes are also interested in Ayurveda. Following table shows details regarding the tourists interested in Ayurveda.

⁶ Anupama Sharma (2013), Medical tourism : emerging challenges and future prospects, International Journal of Business and Management Invention ,Volume No. 2, Issue No.1 , ISSN (Online): 2319 –8028, ISSN (Print): 2319 –801X, PP. 21-29, January.

⁷ Bindu. V. T and Sivakami.V(2016),Customer Satisfaction and Service quality Gap Analysis of Health Tourism in Kerala, Journal of Exclusive Management Science , Volume. No.5, Issue. No. 9, ISSN: 2277-5684, PP.1-12, September.

⁸ Kaboor .A and Somashekar .C (2018), Customer Perception towards Health Tourism in Karnataka, International Journal of Engineering and Management Research ,Volume No.8,Issue No.01,Online ISSN 2249-2585 Print ISSN 2249-8672, PP.1-13, January.

Desire	No of health tourist	percentage
Strongly agree	270	45.94
No opinion	7	42.16
Disagree	156	1.89
Strongly disagree	3	0.81

Majority of health tourists would like to recommend Ayurveda treatment to others and 9.19 percent of them are not interested in Recommending Ayurveda treatment to their friends and relatives. 1.89 percent Of the health tourists have no opinion about recommending Ayurveda treatment to their friends and relatives

AYURVEDA SYSTEM:

'Ayurveda' literally means "Science of Life". Ayurveda is evolved from the various Vedic hymns rooted in

- The fundamental philosophies about life, disease and health. The Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita,
- Developed around 2500 BC, are the main treatises of Ayurveda fully available today.
- According to Ayurveda, fitness is considered a precondition for obtain the goals of life i.e., Dharma, Artha, Kama and Moksha.
- Ayurveda takes an integrated view of the physical, mental, spiritual and social aspects of human beings and about the inter relationships among these aspects.

The philosophy of Ayurveda is based on the theory of Panchmahabhutas (five Primordial treatments)

ORIGIN OF MEDICAL TOURISM:

- Our Indian system of remedy like Ayurveda and Unani system of medicine for the same cause were very eminent and popular from poles apart countries come for their cure and mending.
- In Roman Britain, patients take the waters at a shrine at Bath, a practice that continued for 2,000 years commencing the 18th century affluent Europeans travelled to spas commencing Germany to the Nile. At First, mere travelling was measured to be a fine remedy for cerebral and corporal fit creature Spa
- Towns and sanatoriums may be considered an early form of medical tourism. In eighteenth Century England, for example, patients visited spas because they were places with supposedly. Health-giving mineral waters, treating diseases from gout to liver disorders and bronchitis

Scope of Health Tourism and present status in India:

Health Tourism holds immense hope. The Indian systems of medicines, i.e. Ayurveda, Yoga, Panchakarma, Rejuvenation Therapy, etc. are among the most Ancient systems of medical treatment, of the world. India can provide Medical and Health care at international standard at comparatively low cost. Southern States of India, especially Kerala, has developed Health Tourism as one of the products for the Promotion of tourism in Kerala. Health Tourism has also been promoted as one of the USP's of the State. Most of the hotels/resorts are coming up with the Ayurveda Centres as an integral part. Most of the foreign tourists are now coming to India only for Ayurveda. The leading tour operators have included Ayurveda in their brochures.

Promoting Health Tourism worldwide:

The growth of Medical and Health Tourism in India can be much higher if Adequate focus is given to Health and Medical Tourism. Some of the main Advantages that India has are as under:

- It has world-class doctors and hospitals
- The cost of the treatment is a fraction of cost in the source markets
- There is no waiting period for various medical processes
- Increasing popularity of India as a tourist destination in the west
- Eastern Healthcare Wisdom along with the expertise of Western Medicine.

Process:

The typical process for medical tourism is as follows: the person seeking medical treatment abroad contacts a medical tourism provider. The provider usually requires the patient to provide a medical report, including the nature of ailment, local doctors' opinion, medical history, and diagnosis, and may request additional information. Certified medical doctors or consultants then advise on the medical treatment. The approximate expenditure, choice of hospitals and tourist destination, and duration of stay etc. is discussed. After signing consent bonds and agreements, the patient is given recommendation letter for a medical visa, to be procured from the concerned embassy. The patient travels to the destination country, where the medical tourism provider assigns a case executive, who takes care of the patient's accommodation, treatment and any other form of care. Once the treatment is done, the patient can remain in the tourist destination or return home. The study will aim to study the potential of medical tourism and find out the areas where more and more foreign tourists can be attracted for medical services. Further the study will also focus on how foreign exchange earnings can be increased by further promoting India's medical tourism globally by blending the Prime Ministers initiative of „Make in India“. **Analysis** Case tries to compare the three dimensions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is a way of systematically solving the research problem.

It deals with the research design used for the present study. A pilot study was done to evaluate the awareness on medical tourists who visit for ayurvedic treatments.

Particulars	No Of Respondents	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Below 20	36	18.0	18.0	18.0
20-40	82	41.0	41.0	59.0
40-60	64	32.0	32.0	91.0
above 60 years	18	9.0	9.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Government had taken initiatives in Medical tourism:

India is envisioned as a medical tourism hub by our Government. Various medical tourism accreditation bodies like International Society for Quality in Healthcare (ISQAH), Joint Commission International (JCI) approved various hospitals to this effect.

- Several policies were initiated to enable the journey of the medical tourists by introducing a separate category of medical visa: M-Visa. This visa can be extended for additional 12 months beyond the 1 year issue period. A no-hindrance-clearance has been provided for medical tourists at the airport. A separate medical escort visa (MX) for accompanying relatives has also been introduced.
- India has proved to be a wellness destination for global travellers. Realizing this capability, Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India is formulating guidelines and policies to promote wellness tourism of India. India is participating in several wellness programmes thereby promoting its wellness programs. The Ministry of Tourism will also give financial assistance to wellness centres' accredited National Board for Accreditation of Hospitals and Healthcare Services.
- The Government of Kerala has always tried to promote ayurveda under the banner of healthcare tourism and has classified Ayurveda centres' into two categories – Green leaf and Olive leaf – a sort of grading the ayurveda centres'. Kerala Tourism Development Corporation (KTDC) has also tied up with reputed centres' of Ayurveda for delivering genuine and treatments to their international tourists.

- Dedicated Exhibition Space for Medical Tourism in ITB, Berlin- In order to promote the positioning of India as a Medical destination and increase the presence of the medical fraternity in the international travel exhibitions, a dedicated space of 4 sq. m. was provided to the medical fraternity within the India Pavilion at ITB, Berlin. Govt. of India has also taken part in a couple of medical tourism faire and events across the globe in the past few years to promote Medical Tourism in India like 'Arab Health', 'Namaskar Africa', 'European Medical Travel Conference' , 'Medi Tour Expo' etc. (<http://incredibleindia.org/index.php/trade-product/products/medical-tourism/about-the-product>)

Type of Ayurveda Provider chosen for Treatment

Ayurveda providers	No of health tourists	Percentage
Holiday resorts	147	55.89
Ayurvedic Hospitals	85	32.32
Multispecialty hospitals	31	11.79
Total	263	100

Conclusion:

"Make in India" initiative gives enough opportunities for Medical tourism in terms of identified sectors viz. Tourism & Hospitality and Wellness. Few more sectors can be analysed which can have impact on promoting medical tourism viz. Construction and Aviation which will create infrastructure and increase connectivity of Metros with the rest of the world. India can also create Health-Hubs to attract more tourists for wellness.